

Selling and monetizing data in B2B markets: Four data-driven value propositions

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Data
Digital servitization
Value proposition
Revenue model
Monetization
Value capture

ABSTRACT

Data has become a powerful source of competitive advantage in contemporary business-to-business (B2B) markets, enabling vendors to create enhanced and completely new value propositions. However, while many firms can generate a lot of data from their businesses, they struggle to translate it into sellable offerings. To address this issue, this study examines how firms can sell and monetize data in B2B markets. Based on an extensive multiple case study, this study identifies four archetypical data-driven value propositions (data as a product, data-enhanced products, data-driven services, and data-enabled performance outcomes) and illuminates the key data-related capabilities and challenges related to each value proposition. The findings contribute to the digital servitization and data monetization literatures by illustrating how industrial firms can harness, package, and monetize data in B2B markets. For managers, this study offers important insights into the various strategies and capabilities needed to sell and monetize data in B2B markets.

1. Introduction

The amount and availability of data that firms can generate and collect in contemporary business-to-business (B2B) markets are growing rapidly and exponentially (Ritter and Pedersen 2020; Wedel and Kannan 2016). While widely known data-driven businesses are often in the business-to-consumer space (Acciarini et al., 2023), the idea of creating and capturing value from data is also rapidly increasing in the contemporary B2B space. Harnessing and leveraging data provides a powerful source of competitive advantage by offering opportunities to increase productivity through automated and efficient processes (Côte-Real et al. 2020; Ulaga and Reinartz 2011) and create enhanced or completely new and data-driven value propositions (Parvinen et al., 2020; Porter and Heppelmann 2014; Sorescu 2017). Consequently, many traditional equipment manufacturers have shifted toward developing and deploying intelligent products and smart services that allow them to collect and analyze product usage and process data to create better customer outcomes (Firouzi et al., 2022; Gebauer et al., 2020; Raddats et al. 2022). Some firms in B2B markets have also been established around “pure data” value propositions (Mosch et al., 2022). However, despite increasing investments in developing data-driven offerings, many B2B firms still struggle to sell and monetize their data

(Bean and Davenport 2019; Gandhi et al., 2018; Liozu and Ulaga 2018).

The transition of B2B firms toward data-driven offerings has been extensively discussed in the digital servitization literature, which considers how firms can move from traditional products to digital solutions by using data and develop enhanced or completely new product-service offerings (Kohtamäki et al., 2019; Paschou et al., 2020). While this literature has provided rich insights into different business models (Kohtamäki et al., 2022), digital service transformation journeys (Chen et al., 2021; Visnjic et al. 2022), and organizational capabilities (Hasselblatt et al., 2018; Marcon et al., 2022) that can help develop data-driven offerings, it offers less information about how B2B firms can sell and monetize data-driven value propositions. This is an important issue since the (in)ability to generate new revenue streams from data-driven offerings is a major barrier that hinders B2B firms' growth toward digital offerings (Gebauer et al., 2020).

Data monetization refers to using data to generate quantifiable economic benefits that can be translated into cost savings or additional revenues (Gartner 2022; Liozu and Ulaga 2018). Data involves significant economic potential due to its transferability and reconfigurability into value-creating objects (Alaimo and Kallinikos 2022; Jones and Tonetti 2020). However, unlocking this potential involves challenges related to competitive and legal issues (Nguyen and Paczos 2020; Ritala

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2023.102935>

Received 14 February 2022; Received in revised form 7 November 2023; Accepted 1 December 2023

Available online 30 December 2023

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and Karhu 2023), privacy (Quach et al., 2022), organizational and technical issues (Mirbagherimarvili et al. 2022), and the lack of general market structures for selling data (Koutroumpis et al. 2020). Data monetization can be viewed internally or externally (Gandhi et al., 2018); we focus on external data monetization strategies that firms in B2B markets can use to generate enhanced or new revenue streams by selling data as part of their value propositions, which is often the most challenging way to monetize data (Wixom and Ross 2017). While previous research suggests that firms can adopt three different ways for external data monetization that focus on selling raw data, data-based analyses, or data-based services (Buff et al. 2015; Gandhi et al., 2018; Parvinen et al., 2020), it provides less insights on the specific data-related capabilities and challenges related to each approach, as well as the requirements and barriers that drive or hinder the transition from one approach to another.

Consequently, the purpose of this study is to examine how B2B firms can sell and monetize data by addressing two research questions: RQ1) What kind of data-driven value propositions B2B firms use? RQ2) What are the key capabilities and challenges related to different data-driven value propositions? We draw empirical insights from an extensive multiple case study that includes three different data sets (20 documented client case studies, interviews with 15 managers at 14 firms, and 20 publicly available case examples) and spans a wide range of B2B industries and offerings.

Our findings identify four different data-driven value propositions that range from selling i) data as a product, ii) data-enhanced products, iii) data-driven services, and iv) data-enabled performance outcomes, and illustrate alternative ways to sell and monetize data in B2B markets. Furthermore, we highlight the key characteristics of each data-driven value proposition and develop a continuum that shows how firms can transition between different data-driven value propositions and productize, servitize, and performatize their data resources.

Taken together, the findings contribute to the digital servitization and data monetization literatures by explaining how B2B firms can harness, package, and monetize data in B2B markets. This responds to recent calls for a better understanding of alternative value capture methods and revenue models that exploit data in digital servitization (Kohtamäki et al., 2022) and extend the nascent data monetization research by providing a more granular understanding of the potential pathways to capture value from data in B2B markets (Gandhi et al., 2018; Parvinen et al., 2020).

2. Literature review and conceptual background

2.1. Digital servitization and data-driven value creation

Digital servitization is one of the most active research areas in both recent research and managerial practice and aims to understand how B2B firms create new types of value with digital technologies (Favoretto et al., 2022; Kohtamäki et al., 2022; Kowalkowski et al. 2022). Combining the ideas of digitalization and servitization, it describes how firms can deploy digital technologies to enhance their existing product-service offerings and develop smart solutions and product-service-software systems (Kohtamäki et al., 2021; Paschou et al., 2020). These can range from intelligent products and remote or predictive maintenance services to connected systems, automated solutions, and digital platforms and include technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), Big Data, predictive analytics, and cloud computing (Ardolino et al., 2018; Paiola and Gebauer 2020; Porter and Heppelmann 2014).

Given that digital servitization combines two major shifts, it is a wide-reaching phenomenon involving “the transformation in processes, capabilities, and offerings within B2B firms and their associate ecosystems to progressively create, deliver, and capture increased service value arising from a broad range of enabling digital technologies” (Kamalaldin et al., 2020, p. 478). While digital servitization involves

changes in many areas, touches many actors, and fundamentally changes the business logic of both firms and their ecosystems (Kohtamäki et al., 2020; Makkonen et al., 2022; Marcon et al., 2022), its core purpose is the utilization of digital technologies to help firms create, deliver, and capture more value from service-based offerings.

However, digital technologies alone do not create and deliver more value; rather, it is the *data* that these technologies enable firms to access and generate. This can include, for example, data on the location, condition, and usage of products, the preferences and behaviors of customers, and the performance of business processes (Porter and Heppelmann 2014). By collecting, analyzing, and leveraging data, firms can create enhanced and new service offerings that deliver more value for themselves and their customers (Gebauer et al., 2020; Raddats et al. 2022; Ritala and Karhu 2023). For example, improved access to customers’ product usage and process data enables vendors to remotely diagnose and optimize product and process performance (Uлага and Reinartz 2011), proactively carry out and automate different service activities, equipment upgrades, and software updates (Allmendinger and Lombreglia 2005; Coreynen et al. 2017), and connect multiple products, components, and systems for better functionality across networks and ecosystems (Jovanovic et al. 2022; Porter and Heppelmann 2014). While data has the potential to boost value creation for all types of offerings, its role and importance increase as firms move along the (digital) servitization continuum and transition from product-centric value propositions to business models that deliver usage and performance outcomes (Coreynen et al. 2017; Ghosh et al., 2021; Kohtamäki et al., 2019).¹

While the existing digital servitization literature has described several business models that B2B firms can use to develop data-driven offerings (for reviews, see Kohtamäki et al., 2019, 2022), they tend to emphasize the business model elements needed to create value from data but pay less attention to the elements required to capture value from data (cf. Cappa et al., 2021; Urbinati et al., 2019). Consequently, generating a better understanding of the alternative methods and models that B2B firms can use to capture value from data is highlighted as a priority area for contemporary digital servitization research (Kohtamäki et al., 2022).

2.2. Value capture and data monetization

Value capture is the process of securing financial or nonfinancial return from value creation and is often conceptualized as the customer’s willingness to pay (or buy), thus generating revenues that the supplier can appropriate (Chesbrough et al. 2018; Lepak et al. 2007). While the digital servitization research has provided extensive insights into what is needed to create value from data (e.g., Kohtamäki et al., 2022), only a few digital servitization studies consider how firms can capture value from data. Furthermore, those studies tend to focus on internal performance improvements (Cappa et al., 2021; Trabucchi et al. 2017; Urbinati et al., 2019) rather than new revenue generation opportunities (for exceptions, see Gebauer et al., 2021; Hartmann et al., 2016), or describing the value that firms or their customers capture (Chen et al., 2021; Raddats et al., 2019) rather than explaining what firms need to do or how they can capture that value from data.

Data monetization refers to a process that allows firms to capture monetary value from data, and more broadly, to generate revenue from selling data and data-based products and services (Mirbagherimarvili et al. 2022). While data monetization is sometimes described as converting the intangible value of data into real value (Najjar and Kettinger 2013), turning data insights into action (McKinsey 2017), or creating

¹ The product-service-systems (PSS) literature (for a review, see Waidelich et al., 2019), a sub-stream of servitization research, has also demonstrated the shift from product-oriented toward use-oriented systems and ultimately to results-oriented PSSs (Raddats et al., 2019; Reim et al. 2015; Tukker 2004).

value from data assets (Gartner 2020), its core purpose is to use data to create measurable economic benefits through new revenue streams or profits (Liozu and Ulaga 2018). Firms can generally monetize data either internally by optimizing business decisions and processes or externally by selling data-driven offerings to new and existing customers (Quach et al., 2022; Wixom and Ross 2017). This study focuses on the latter perspective, exploring how firms can sell and monetize data-driven value propositions.

Data monetization is often considered through a business model or value proposition lens (for a review on data and business models, see Acciarini et al., 2023). This literature explains how firms can make money by selling data to customers and/or other external partners and has highlighted different ways to categorize data monetization approaches. For example, Schüritz and Satzger (2016) demonstrate how firms can infuse data into value creation, value capture, and value proposition and adopt business models that incorporate data into each of those elements. Other scholars have proposed different typologies for how data can be packaged into sellable offerings. For example, Buff et al. (2015) distinguish between data offerings, insight offerings, and action offerings, Gandhi et al. (2018) between data, insights, and data platforms as a service, and Parvinen et al. (2020) between raw data, data analyses, and data services. Thomas et al. (2023) further distinguish between data supply, data factory, data service, and data platform-based business models (see also Thomas and Leiponen 2016). However, while selling data is sometimes seen as an easy way to success since many companies already have access to it (Lewis and McKone 2016), data monetization is not as straightforward in reality; one key reason for that is how the nature of data assets differs from other resources (Quach et al., 2022; Wixom and Ross 2017).

While the key benefit of data is usually its non-rival nature, which means that once acquired, firms can reuse and resell it with little or even no additional costs (Jones and Tonetti 2020), capturing value from data also involves some unique challenges. First, firms need different digital technologies, sensors, and interfaces to collect the data, including IoT (Markfort et al., 2022) or software-based sensors (Subramaniam et al., 2022). Second, firms also need specialized data analytics (Wixom and Ross 2017), data processing and interpretation (Ulaga and Reinartz 2011), and data science and AI (Alfaro et al., 2019; Firouzi et al., 2022) capabilities to translate raw data into actionable and revenue-generating insights and embed data into value-adding product and service offerings (Lange et al. 2021). In addition, depending on where and how data is collected and what category it represents (proprietary, personal, etc.), there might be legal, regulatory, security, privacy, functional, or ownership-related barriers to using or commercializing it (Jones and Tonetti 2020; Mirbagherimarvili et al. 2022; Nguyen and Paczos 2020). Due to these different challenges in utilizing and commercializing data, firms need to consider strategically how and to what extent they can monetize the data they can access (Quach et al., 2022). Finally, there can also be challenges with customer or industry maturity in terms of accepting and using novel data-driven solutions, which often require extra effort from suppliers to educate and shape those markets (Koutroumpis et al. 2020).

3. Methodology

To examine how firms in B2B markets sell and monetize data, we adopted an abductive research design and extensive multiple case study approach (Dubois and Gadde 2002, 2014). An abductive research design is particularly suitable for areas where theoretical frameworks already exist but provide only a limited or incomplete understanding of the focal phenomena (Tavory and Timmermans 2014). This allows researchers to build on existing models and complementary theories while simultaneously drawing new insights from empirical observations and then iteratively continue this process until the emerging findings provide better explanations for the observed reality (Dubois and Gadde 2002, 2014).

The multiple case study approach allows researchers to examine the focal phenomenon within and between different contexts (Yin 2018). This is particularly suitable for complex phenomena like data-driven value propositions that manifest differently in specific industry contexts (Hartmann et al., 2016). Adopting the multiple case approach allows us to develop rich and holistic insights by comparing multiple firms across a range of B2B industries and analyzing empirical insights from several types of information-rich primary and secondary data sources (Eisenhardt and Graebner 2007).

3.1. Data collection and analysis process

Our data collection and analysis proceeded in tandem over three main stages (See Fig. 1). In the first stage, we applied convenience and purposive sampling (Patton 2015) and derived early insights from 20 illustrative and confidential client case studies that focused on B2B firms' transformation toward data-driven business models and value propositions. We gained access to these case studies through one of the authors, who had previously worked at one of Finland's leading digital technology companies, consulting and advising other firms on their transformation toward data-driven businesses models and selling and monetizing data. Our sampling strategy focused on identifying all the documented client case studies from the consulting firm's portfolio that involved B2B firms. All the included firms were then asked for consent to use their case studies for analysis. To avoid any ethical or legal conflicts, we do not disclose any company-specific information about the analyzed client case studies. All the client case studies were originally documented as case memos that described a client's data-driven business model, the type of data used, how it was embedded in that firm's core offering, and what kinds of revenue models were used.

To analyze the client case studies, we used exploratory and data-driven coding to identify various data-driven value propositions and their key characteristics. At this stage, our analysis focused on capturing and comparing i) the kind(s) of data-driven offerings that firms sold, ii) the key customer benefit that the data enabled firms to deliver, and iii) the main revenue model for the firm (see rows 2–4 in Table 2). At the end of stage 1, we had identified six preliminary categories that emerged from the data and described different data-driven value propositions and their key characteristics.

In the second stage, we used purposive sampling (Patton 2015) and identified 14 B2B firms that operated in different industries, sold data-driven offerings, and represented different categories that were identified during the previous stage (see Table 1 for case descriptions). We conducted interviews with 15 managers from these firms to gain deeper insights into their strategies and capabilities and the challenges they faced related to selling and monetizing data. The interviews took 49 min on average and were digitally recorded and transcribed verbatim, resulting in 102 single-spaced pages of text for analysis and coding.

During this stage, we conducted two primary analytical activities. First, we compared the preliminary findings from stage 1 with the literature on digital servitization (Kohtamäki et al., 2019), product-service systems (Tukker 2004), data monetization (Buff et al. 2015; Parvinen et al., 2020), and B2B selling and value propositions (Keränen et al. 2021; Ulaga and Reinartz 2011). Guided by these insights, we merged² two conceptually overlapping categories into the remaining four categories. Next, we used focused coding (Saldana 2015) to analyze our interview data from 14 B2B firms to elaborate and expand on our interpretations of the four remaining categories that represented different data-driven value propositions. In particular, we sought new

² The two merged categories were originally labeled as data platforms and data assets, but due to their conceptual and operational similarity to data as a product and data-driven services categories, we decided to merge them with other categories after reviewing the literature.

Fig. 1. Overview of key stages in the abductive data collection and analysis process.

insights into the sources, ownership, capabilities, and challenges related to the data that underpinned each value proposition (see rows 5–9 in Table 2). Fig. 2 presents an example of the coding structure for data-related capabilities and challenges. At the end of stage 2, we had refined and expanded the content of the four categories for different data-driven value propositions.

In the third stage, we used purposive sampling (Patton 2015) and identified 20 new and publicly available cases that illustrated globally known firms and their strategies for selling and monetizing data. The illustrative examples were primarily drawn from academic and practitioner journals (e.g., Ardolino et al., 2018; Pardo et al. 2020; Porter and Heppelmann 2014) and were spread relatively evenly across the four remaining categories. We used focused coding (Saldana 2015) to analyze this data, with the goal of further refining, illustrating, and validating the emerging findings. By the end of this stage, we had refined and enriched the content of the remaining four categories for different data-driven value propositions. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the key stages in the data collection and analysis process, while Table 2 summarizes the key findings.

3.2. Research quality

To improve the quality and credibility of our data analysis and empirical interpretations, we used several forms of triangulation (Farquhar et al. 2020). Researcher triangulation involved using four researchers with different academic and industry backgrounds in the data analysis. In line with recommendations for using a pluralistic approach

for data analysis (Welch and Piekkari 2017), this allowed us to apply different perspectives and knowledge bases and to co-develop diverse meanings and interpretations for the emerging findings. Theory triangulation involved applying multiple theoretical lenses from different literature streams, which enabled us to leverage pre-existing frameworks, models, and vocabularies from different disciplines to aid and shape the development and emergence of our empirical interpretations (cf. Andersen and Kragh 2010). Data triangulation included generating empirical insights from three different datasets that featured different types of data sources (case studies, interviews, illustrative examples) and a diverse set of B2B firms that operate in different industries, sell different offerings, and leverage different types of data in their value propositions. This allowed us to expand, corroborate, and converge empirical insights from different sources, thus enhancing the validity of the study and verifying our interpretations. Finally, we sent summaries of the emerging findings to study participants for member checking and validation.

4. Findings

Based on our data analysis, we identified four archetypical data-driven value propositions that B2B firms use to sell and monetize their data. While some companies used only one type of value proposition, others employed several value propositions concurrently, as indicated in Table 1. Thus, while we delineate four different data-driven value propositions, in reality, it is possible that one firm can employ one or more of the identified value propositions simultaneously. In section 4.5,

Table 1
Overview of the interview data.

Firm (<i>n</i> = 14)	Industry	Employees	Informants (<i>n</i> = 15)	Business description	Primary value proposition
Arvova	Software	3–5	CEO	Finnish startup that helps B2B companies manage customer value and build better businesses with their customer value analysis tool. Uses data to make creating, measuring, and communicating customer value more transparent.	Data as a product
Platform of Trust	Software	40–50	Chief Operations Officer	Finnish startup that sells a decentralized data-sharing platform that enables data to flow from various systems to different applications and interfaces in the built environment.	Data as a product
EagleAlpha	Data solution/ software	30	Head of Data Sourcing & Advisory	Irish company selling “alternative data,” acting as an agent between two parties: data owners who lack access to qualified investors and investors such as private equity companies that need reliable data to help them make better investment decisions.	Data as a product
SalesLeaderSoft ^a	Software	150	Sales Lead	Sells access to software-as-a-service (SaaS) platform to help salespeople and marketers in other B2B companies. The firm’s technology collects, reads, and understands data on companies and businesses and creates real-time company insights that are directly applicable to its customers’ business systems.	Data as a product
Telia	Telecom	21,000	Head of Business Analytics	Large Northern European telecom operator that provides various communication services for consumers and businesses. For business customers, it uses aggregated and anonymized customer location data to provide insights into citizen activity for urban planning.	Data as a product
Metso Outotec	Mining	15,000	Remote Services Product Manager	A Finnish-based large global corporation that sells technology and services for mining and metal refining industries. Uses data collected from its own equipment to provide predictive maintenance and remote control services for its clients.	Data-enhanced products; Data-driven services
Kyndryl	Information technology	90,000	Digital Transformation Leader	A large global corporation that sells information technology infrastructure management services to B2B clients. Customer and partner data is used in designing and managing technology systems, such as cloud solutions, networks, data and AI, security applications, and digital workspaces.	Data-driven services
Jakamo	Software	10–15	CBDO	Finnish startup that sells a software platform to manufacturing companies. Transparent data sharing and collaboration between manufacturers and their suppliers enable increased productivity along the supply chain.	Data-driven services
ExploderCorp ^a	Mining	15,000	Coordinator Asset Information (Global)	Global provider of commercial explosives and related systems to the mining, quarrying, oil and gas, and construction industries. Customers’ operations data on the firm’s platform is used for data analysis, storage, and sharing.	Data-driven services, Data-enabled performance outcomes
HeavyDuty SolutionsCo ^a	Maritime	2000	Director Digital Solutions	Sells cargo and handling solutions to customers in maritime industries. Uses data to offer digitally enabled cargo handling equipment to optimize operations.	Data-enhanced products; Data-driven services; Data-enabled performance outcomes
Hilti	Construction	30,000	Sales Director	Multinational company that sells power tools, system solutions, software, and services to firms in the construction, building maintenance, energy, and manufacturing industries. Uses customer data by analyzing tool usage and construction site activities.	Data-enhanced products; Data-driven services; Data-enabled performance outcomes
Johnson & Johnson MedTech	Pharmaceuticals and medical devices	130,000	Health Economics & Market Access Manager	A global corporation that manufactures medical devices and pharmaceuticals for doctors, hospitals, and consumers. As part of its medical devices business, data is collected from medical workflows, enabling hospitals to augment and automate the analysis of processes and/or operational performance for continued quality improvement.	Data-enhanced products; Data-driven services; Data-enabled performance outcomes
Kemira	Chemicals	5000	Director, Market & App Development (Industry & Water); Director, Market & App Development (Pulp & Paper)	A Finnish-based global company selling chemical solutions, analytics services, and expertise for water-intensive industries. Collects real-time data on customers’ chemical processing activities with the goal of optimizing chemical application and process performance.	Data-enhanced products; Data-driven services; Data-enabled performance outcomes
ABB	Power and automation	10,000	VP Digital Lead	A large global corporation that sells electrification, automation, and robotic technology and related services to industrial customers. Uses Internet of Things data from its products in the cloud to optimize customer performance; other relevant external data often complement customer data.	Data-enhanced products; Data-driven services; Data-enabled performance outcomes

^a Pseudonyms applied for confidentiality purposes.

Table 2
An overview of the four archetypical data-driven value propositions.^a

	DATA AS A PRODUCT	DATA-ENHANCED PRODUCTS	DATA-DRIVEN SERVICES	DATA-ENABLED PERFORMANCE OUTCOMES
Key idea	Raw data is sold (or shared via a digital platform) to another party	Existing product or service offering is enhanced with data	Data is used to optimize customers' business or organizational processes	Data is used to deliver performance and/or capacity
What is being sold	Raw data and insights, analysis, and reports based on data	Data-enhanced product offerings	Diagnostic, audit, training, and consulting services based on data	Guaranteed and measurable performance outcomes based on data
Key customer benefit	Access to new knowledge and information	Optimized product and usage experiences	Process optimization	Realized performance outcomes and available capacity
Revenue model	Product-based or subscription	Product-based premium pricing; data included in the product price	Service and consulting fees (work- or performance-based)	Premium pricing based on realized use value; subscription
Data source	Any data	Product usage data	Customers' process, operations, and performance data	Customers' process, operations, and performance data
Data ownership	The customer gets access to or ownership of the data	The vendor retains ownership of the data	The vendor gains access to the customer's data	The vendor owns its data and gets access to the customer's data; customers gain access to their own process data.
Data-related vendor capabilities	Data collection, analysis, and interpretation capabilities	Product development and monitoring capabilities	(Customer) data analysis and consulting capabilities	Performance outcome prediction and control capabilities
Data-related vendor activities	Packaging data into a product that can be sold or shared with other parties	Embedding data into a physical product to create smart functionalities	Deriving insights from the data to optimize customer's business and organizational processes	Using data to take responsibility for customers' processes
Key challenge	Data ownership, privacy, and legal risks; customers' challenges with large and/or un-curated datasets	Customers' (in)ability to use smart features	Access to and quality of customer data; (in)ability to derive data-driven insights	Realization, control, and measurement of performance outcomes

^a For each value proposition type, we have highlighted the most distinctive characteristics. This does not mean that other characteristics would not play any role in different value propositions. For example, data-related vendor capabilities are usually very cumulative in nature, and “stack up” as companies move from simpler to more advanced value propositions.

Exemplary open codes

Fig. 2. Example of a coding structure.

we describe a continuum that illuminates how firms can move from one type of value proposition to another and the requirements and challenges that this transition involves. In the following sections, we detail each data-driven value proposition and its key characteristics using illustrative examples from the data. Table 2 provides an overview of the four data-driven value propositions.

4.1. Data as a product

The key idea of data as a product value proposition is to sell raw or

processed data to customers. With this value proposition, vendors usually sell their own data or data collected from a public domain or other companies. Publicly known examples include Walmart, which sells consumption pattern data for advertisers, Vodafone, which sells raw location data to TomTom, and LiveRamp, a data broker that consolidates and sells data from multiple public and external sources.

In our case data, Telia offers a good example of a vendor selling its own company data; it sells crowd insights based on location data collected from its mobile network: “Crowd insights are based on selling insights on how people move. ... It’s not only enhancing, but the actual

offering is the data.” Some firms collect publicly available data and integrate and curate it in a form that is easy for customers to use. For example, EagleAlpha and SalesLeaderSoft collect and sell industry- and company-specific data to help their customers with sales, marketing, investment, and industry analyses. Similarly, Arvova collects customer-, market-, and/or industry-related data and sells it either as one-off analyses and strategic reports or as an ongoing subscription service. In addition, data intermediaries and integrators can sell and transfer data across different parties. For example, Platform of Trust offers value propositions that allow the intermediation of data from one organization to another; the added value of productizing data takes place when a vendor makes it possible for different companies’ data to be exchanged in a secure, curated, and standardized format.

By buying data as a product, customers gain new knowledge and information about their target market that would have otherwise been inaccessible. Vendors usually use either product- or subscription-based pricing models to obtain such data, depending on whether the data is sold on a transactional (i.e., individual reports and analyses) or continuous basis (real-time market analyses, data dashboards, tools, etc.), where the premium depends on the value and scarcity of the data.

With data as a product, the underlying data is often related to specific products, markets, or value chains (e.g., buying criteria or customer preferences in a specific industry or for specific products, investment opportunities in a particular industry, or a list of supplier companies in a specific sector). To create and deliver this type of value proposition, vendors need data collection, analysis, and interpretation capabilities that enable packaging data into products that can be sold to other partners. For example, SalesLeaderSoft has developed a technical team of over 50 people dedicated to gathering data using different data crawlers and machine learning. However, simply collecting and sharing raw data is rarely enough. Vendors must also know how to analyze and translate data-derived insights like visualizations or reports into customer benefits that can be effectively communicated to customers. For example, Arvova collects data from specific customer industries and markets and translates it into benchmark reports and specific business recommendations. Selling data as a product thus means that the vendor needs to have high data literacy to successfully deliver a data product that customers find valuable and useable. The capabilities required include not only collection and analysis of data but also its “productization” in a meaningful way. In turn, customers who buy data as a product might need some data interpretation and integration capabilities, depending on whether they buy non-processed raw data or curated and processed reports and analyses. For example, as the Eagle Alpha representative explained,

“It’s an expensive process, it’s not just buying the data. You have to have data engineers, data scientists, and data analysts. You have to buy the tech, pay Amazon Cloud, or whatever. Having the expertise, tech, and all the rest of it is the first process. And being able to do it all is the first challenge before you start working with the data itself.... They may not be able to take in the raw data. They may want it aggregated because they don’t have the capabilities, they don’t have data scientists. So they’re looking for less expensive, aggregated data that they can just work with.”

When selling data as a product, vendors typically face challenges related to data ownership and legal risks, especially for data intermediaries whose customers face uncertainty over data ownership, access rights, and regulatory risks. As the informant from Platform of Trust explained, the main concern of customers is not information system risks but rather legal issues: “They are fearing that something in the data that they release as the product is something that is violating someone’s rights or against the GDPR.” Firms that collect data on their own, whether from their customer base or public sources, usually face fewer privacy issues. For instance, Telia sells aggregated location data based on its customers, and the aggregation aspect helps avoid the pitfalls of individual data privacy issues. However, sometimes the aggregation of data can be a double-edged sword, as it might obscure the original data

sources, making it challenging to understand and verify specific ownership, access, and regulatory issues.

4.2. Data-enhanced products

The key idea of selling data-enhanced products is to take existing product offerings and enhance them with data. With this value proposition, vendors still sell physical products, but they are now embedded with smart sensors, intelligent technologies, software, and IoT applications. This allows vendors to collect, analyze, and monitor data on how, where, and when customers use their products. Subsequently, by leveraging this data, vendors can provide new product features and functionalities, such as remote and real-time monitoring, location, and condition diagnostics and automated software updates and upgrades. Known examples of this category include various smart products such as Continental’s smart truck tires, KONE smart elevators, and Konecranes’ smart cranes (Pardo et al., 2020), which include embedded sensors to continuously collect data, on which different smart functionalities can be added to complement the physical product.

Among our case companies, we observed this data-driven value proposition in several product categories. For example, Hilti sells smart, connected power tools that indicate when they are due for maintenance, repair, or calibration, allowing Hilti to monitor, manage, and optimize the condition of entire tool fleets based on product usage data. Metso Outotec and HeavyDutySolutionsCo sell complex and integrated mining industry and load handling systems, respectively, and both augment their equipment and systems with sensors, process analytics, and IoT applications that enable remote monitoring, predictive maintenance, and process optimization. Furthermore, while Kemira and Johnson & Johnson MedTech sell chemical products and pharmaceutical products, respectively, they are increasingly augmenting their product offerings with usage data that helps their customers improve process quality and process efficiency by, for example, optimizing the volumes of products used or in stock in different processes.

Ultimately, the collection and analysis of product usage data help vendors design and develop better products and deliver optimized product usage experiences for their target customers. HeavyDutySolutionsCo identifies such benefits in the customer experience by recognizing that data from their equipment helps them both “to improve time to fix when some problem occurs[and] ... prevent the failure” from occurring in the first place. By embedding their products with data, vendors can enhance the differentiation power for products that are otherwise relatively similar to competing alternatives, and they typically include data-driven benefits in their premium product price. In some cases, though, vendors can also unbundle the data and sell the software or access to the data from the software as a potential add-on to basic products, with the software then priced based on a subscription logic. For example, Hilti, the power tools provider, sells its On-Track software for tracking tools both as an add-on to and bundled with its product offering, depending on customer needs and/or service level agreements. For Kemira, which sells chemical products, and Metso Outotec, the mining equipment provider, pricing includes a variety of bundling alternatives. Metso Outotec charges a “one-off fee that the customer pays to get connected, to set up the platform, and to set up the data collection and then a monthly fee for the service.”

With data-enhanced products, the underlying data is typically the product usage and process data. Since it is collected from or via the vendor’s products (used on the customers’ premises), vendors usually retain ownership of the data, meaning there are few privacy or sharing issues from the customer side. However, to create and deliver this value proposition, vendors need both data-related collection, analysis, and interpretation capabilities and product development and monitoring capabilities to embed data into physical products and monitor how customers use them.

For example, Hilti has developed a new battery technology that stores and shares product usage information in the cloud and employs

specialist service and software teams that monitor, educate, and assist customers in their power tool usage processes. In turn, customers may need new capabilities and skills in using data-enhanced products so as to optimize their functionality. As a representative from Hilti pointed out, “in most cases, it’s not just about providing them [customers] with a [data-enhanced] asset management solution or a certain type of a tool. It’s change management in the organization and facilitating that.” Many informants also emphasized the importance of acquiring the new capabilities that vendors need to master the data and product interface. For example, one of the interviewees from Kemira noted that on top of the more traditional process and application knowledge, it also now needs to develop and deploy capabilities in digital technologies and interfaces. Similar capability requirements were also noted by the informant from HeavyDutySolutionsCo:

“We need different competencies for different kinds of use cases.... If I want to clear the simulation, we need a simulation engineer. If I’m creating a predictive model, we need a data scientist. But one common thread, which at least from my experience, I’ve observed, is that what we need in the industry more and more is people who can play roles in the intersection of two different competence pools – which means that I need a data scientist who understands the engineering of a pump, for example, and that kind of data scientists would be the most effective one to create predictive models.”

When selling data-enhanced products, vendors tend to face two key challenges. The first is whether customers are willing and able to use all the new data-driven product features. If they are too difficult to learn or complex to use, the potential value of the data may not be realized. The second is whether salespeople can communicate the additional benefits from the data enhancements to justify premium pricing. These two challenges highlight the importance of capability capacity building and education on both the customer and vendor sides. The reality is that while the range of data-enhanced products is increasing rapidly, their smart features are still somewhat new to many B2B customers and their employees. Thus, vendors often need to put additional efforts on internal training and customer education. As the manager from Metso Outotec explained,

“Our biggest challenge at the moment is how to simplify the message so that people around the world could sell this and people around the world from the customer side would understand it and trust that the value will be created because it’s a complex service product.”

4.3. Data-driven services

The key idea of selling data-driven services is to use the vendor’s accumulated data to analyze, predict, and optimize customers’ processes. With this value proposition, vendors sell intangible insights and know-how through consulting services, highlighting potential improvement opportunities in customers’ processes. While vendors can (and often do) sell data-driven services either as an add-on to their data-enhanced products (see previous category) or together with “smart solutions” that deliver data-enabled performance outcomes (see next category), it is also possible to sell data-driven services without the accompanying products, even to customers that use competitors’ products. Publicly known examples of this category include a Finnish circular economy services company, Lassila & Tikanoja, which collects data on properties and sells energy-saving services, and IBM, which collects data sets from its customers, uses its Watson technology to analyze the data, and then offers consulting services featuring data-driven insights and recommendations.

In our data, we found several companies that sell or monetize data as a key part of their service offerings. For example, the commercial explosives provider ExploderCorp sells consulting services that optimize customers’ processes, ABB provides equipment and energy optimization services, Jakamo offers data transfer and integration services in supply

chains, and Kyndryl sells information technology (IT) infrastructure and management services. Furthermore, as part of its medical devices business, Johnson & Johnson MedTech offers a solution that collects and visualizes data from surgical workflows, enabling hospitals to automate the analysis of processes and/or operational performance and thus enable continuous quality improvement.

Essentially, the more vendors can collect and accumulate data from different customer operations and processes, the better they can become at deriving and generating data-driven insights that help customers optimize their processes. From the customer perspective, such services are often relatively easy to acquire. In terms of pricing, vendors usually employ subscription models such as software-as-a-service (SaaS) or, as in the case of Jakamo, adopt a case-by-case pricing model due to the heterogeneity of customer cases. There might also be a combination of one-off fees and subscription fees, as with some of Metso Outotec’s customers, who pay a one-off fee to get access to the digital service platform and then a monthly fee for the service. In the case of Kyndryl, it was noted that many of their customers prefer to pay over the lifetime of the deal, further supporting the prevalence of subscription models for data-driven services.

With data-driven services, the underlying data usually comes from the customer’s own processes, is collected from the data-enhanced products, and can be supplemented by external data. For example, medical industry vendor Johnson & Johnson MedTech conducts its own industry studies to produce what it calls “evidence generated” insights to enrich customer data, which adds value to its consultancy service offerings. On the other hand, companies like ABB typically rely on their customers’ data, which they hold in high value and handle with care and integrity:

“The core principle of what we have is that the customer owns their data. That’s a starting belief in our data manifesto, and then they would always know for what we use the data. So we are kind of a custodian, managing the data for them.... When they use the service, they give us permission to use the data for providing these services.”

To create and deliver data-driven service value propositions, vendors usually need two key capabilities. The first is the customer data analysis capabilities that allows them to access, analyze, and interpret data from customers’ processes (as opposed to data from vendors’ products). The second is consulting capabilities, which allow vendors to understand customers’ business processes and how different types of data can be used to improve these processes. Vendors often leverage these capabilities by extracting, accessing, and analyzing specific customers’ process data and then comparing it to their own accumulated data and expertise in similar applications from other industries. However, developing these capabilities often takes time, as vendors need to accumulate enough data to generate valuable and verified insights and develop a deep understanding of different customer processes and their unique characteristics.

For example, Johnson & Johnson MedTech uses its extensive knowledge of global medical and hospital processes to analyze and benchmark its customers’ process data and derives data-driven insights that identify opportunities to improve process quality and operational performance. Similarly, ExploderCorp offers its customers easy access to its proprietary platform, which provides data-driven industry benchmarks and performance insights at every stage of the blasting process. Furthermore, many informants noted that their ability to provide data-driven services to specific customers was often contingent on a customer’s own ability to access and share their data. For example, the informant from ABB explained that there is a sort of “Maslow’s hierarchy for IoT,” in which the customer’s maturity to collect, digitize, and interpret data from their own processes has a major impact on their ability to benefit from data-driven value propositions:

“Our CDO coined a nice term, which was Maslow’s hierarchy for IoT and related industrial digital offerings.... For instance, if you don’t have data

that you have collected related to process, you can't talk about AI applications to transform your business. So you have to start from the basics, and how we can work with the customer depends on where they are on this progression."

When selling data-driven services, the key challenge to vendors is often the availability of and access to customer data, as customers are not always willing to share or able to access it. As the informant from Metso Outotec explained:

"In some places, the data restrictions and even the culture can impact whether the customer is willing to give us their data.... It depends on the customer's own culture; sometimes, they are set on doing things by themselves and managing the whole data analytics or the maintenance management process by themselves, so that's when they are only looking for buying certain bits and pieces from their vendors."

The challenge is not always only about access to data but can also be about the low quality of the available data, and this can make insights either inaccurate, or impossible to derive or integrate with other data or interfaces. To cope with this issue, ABB has established a *"digital clean simulation model to correct input data because otherwise, you end up garbage in, garbage out in these solutions."*

4.4. Data-enabled performance outcomes

The key idea of selling data-enabled performance outcomes is to combine data-enhanced products and data-driven services into complete smart solutions that can deliver performance outcomes. With this value proposition, vendors take over the responsibility for specific processes on behalf of their customers and sell measurable and guaranteed performance and/or capacity and availability outcomes. Publicly known examples include John Deere, which collects data from farms on weather, soil, tractors, and the like and seeks to optimize customer yields based on that data. GE Power collects data from power plants and sells enhanced energy production as a service. MAN Trucks and Bus sells *"truck use as a service"* and optimizes truck location, availability, and condition based on data. In our sample, we found several firms using data collected from customers' processes and systems to deliver performance, including Hilti, Kemira, ABB, Johnson & Johnson MedTech, HeavyDutySolutionsCo, and ExploderCorp.

When buying data-enabled performance outcomes, customers usually outsource selected parts of their operations and processes to the vendor. In other words, the responsibility for delivering a particular performance outcome is transferred from customer to vendor. The pricing logic of this type of value proposition is often value-based; that is, the price is tied to the realized performance outcomes. For example, Hilti bundles products and customer data-driven insights into a tool fleet management solution that reduces customers' total cost of ownership: *"Most of the time, if we've done our job well enough, we'll be able to cut the customer's total cost of ownership down ... making our business case profitable to the customer."* Similarly, Kemira is experimenting with different revenue models that use performance-based pricing, including a *"fixed base fee in a month plus then a KPI bonus which is then set together with the customer."* Naturally, in such cases, data plays a major role in accumulating evidence of how the customer's operations and performance improve and whether specific key performance indicators are met. Similarly, Johnson & Johnson MedTech has adopted advanced value-based agreements and gain-sharing models and even compensates customers if the promised value outcomes are not realized:

"We commit to certain outcomes, to the certain value we deliver. And if it doesn't reach that outcome or the value that we said that hey we believe in this or we reached it for example only partly, we can compensate back, to part of the investment of the customer.... It is not just talk that we bring you value."

With data-enabled performance outcomes, the underlying data

usually comes directly from the customer's own processes and operations. Typically, the vendor maintains ownership of the data-driven performance insights they have generated, and the customer will have access to it. However, the raw process data that is used as a basis for these insights typically remains with the customer. For instance, HeavyDutySolutionsCo explained that *"we don't want to claim the ownership of the data, and we are just the custodian of it to provide a service."* This custodianship can alleviate customers' worries about exposing their proprietary data to external parties.

To create and deliver data-enabled performance outcomes, vendors need deep expertise in their customers' industries and performance outcome prediction and control capabilities. Thus, many vendors in our sample had developed new predictive analytics, algorithms, and software applications that enabled them to model their customers' operations and deliver optimized process outcomes. For example, ExploderCorp has developed its own modeling software, which learns from data collected in mining operations to associate specific rock and ore properties to applied blasting energy. This allows it to control and optimize things like blast hole design, excess drilling explosive consumption, and rock sizing distribution, enabling it to deliver guaranteed blasting process outcomes. Kemira has developed a data-driven chemistry management software package that allows it to monitor, control, and optimize customers' water-treatment processes in real time on their behalf and deliver improved performance and quality outcomes. Similarly, ABB helps its customers by providing software- and data-driven service models that optimize the productivity of large industrial systems.

When selling data-enabled performance outcomes, the key challenge is often the realization, control, and measurement of the outcomes delivered. Vendors must understand and carry the risk that are related to guaranteeing performance improvements, especially as they are realized in the customer's environment where vendors can rarely control all the variables. Fluctuations in customers' processes and operations create challenges to accumulating accurate data-driven insights and require careful consideration of whether it makes sense or is even possible to engage in performance-based pricing. Furthermore, it might be difficult for vendors to demonstrate constant improvement in performance after first achieving the goals that are low-hanging fruits. A quote from one of the Kemira interviewees illustrates both challenges:

"You have such fluctuations [in the customer's processes], so it can be quite tricky [...] That's always the disadvantage with the outcome [based value proposition] because there's always an element of constant improvements, and you can make very steep improvements in the beginning, but then it might be quite slow because of the physical laws what you can actually do."

4.5. Data-driven value proposition continuum: productizing, servitizing, and performatizing data

While B2B firms can use more than one data-driven value proposition simultaneously, they usually start by experimenting with data-based products and move gradually to more complex data-driven services and solutions. This was particularly observable with the vendors in our sample that had extended their initial physical product offering with data-driven features and later services and performance outcomes (including Hilti, Kemira, ABB, Johnson & Johnson MedTech, and HeavyDutySolutionsCo). Fig. 3 depicts the typical transition trajectory that firms follow when they productize, servitize, and performatize data along the data-driven value proposition continuum.

With the increasing availability of data via physical and digital interfaces, many firms have become aware that they have good access to substantial amount of data from their own operations and external markets. To leverage their data as a stand-alone, valuable asset, firms can *productize* it by packaging it into reports and analyses or embedding it into their existing physical products (as visualized in the left-hand side of Fig. 3). This process allows firms to convert and translate data into

Fig. 3. Data-driven value propositions continuum.

new and enhanced products that can be sold for new revenues. While many firms can create value from data by productizing it into different data and data-enhanced products, the typical barrier that hinders productization is usually the lack of technical capabilities to collect, analyze, and interpret data and engineering capabilities to embed data into value-adding products. Thus, the core capabilities needed in data productization relate to product development and packaging or embedding data into relatively standardized or modular products that can be scaled to many customers with relatively little customization. Ultimately, productization aims to create data-driven value propositions that customers can use with relatively independently after a purchase in the form of pure data products or data-driven features embedded in physical products.

As firms continue to experiment with and sell data and data-enhanced products, they accumulate data and insights and gain a better understanding of how data can improve their customers' processes and product usage experiences. To leverage the accumulated data and customer understanding, vendors can *servitize* their data-driven insights into "process support" services (Ulaga and Reinartz 2011) that are geared toward assisting customers in improving their business processes. These data-driven services usually include different consultation, audit, and diagnostic services aimed at analyzing customers' operations and suggesting potential opportunities for improvement. The servitization process enables firms to convert and translate their accumulated product usage and customer process data into new data-driven services that can be sold either as an add-on to existing products or separately as independent services, thus offering new revenue potential for vendors.

Whereas data productization requires more product-centric and technical capabilities, the key barrier that hinders data servitization is usually a lack of the process-centric consulting capabilities needed to access and analyze customer data and understand how different types of data can be used to improve customers' own processes. Thus, when moving from data productization to data servitization, the role of necessary data-related capabilities shifts from enhancing the vendor's products to highlighting improvement opportunities in customers' business processes and supporting more customized and consulting-oriented value propositions instead of product-oriented ones. Naturally, the product-centric and technical capabilities required for data

productization act as a foundation for companies that are considering moving to data servitization.

The better understanding of and access to customer process data vendors gain, the better opportunities they have to monitor, predict, and control customer process outcomes. To capitalize on these opportunities, vendors can *performatize* their data-driven insights and deliver process improvement and performance outcomes. This is similar to "process delegation services" (Ulaga and Reinartz 2011), where the vendor takes responsibility for specific customer processes on behalf of (or together with) the customer. Performatization involves combining products, services, and data into intelligent and smart solutions that deliver optimized process outcomes to the customer. This process enables firms to convert and translate their accumulated data-driven insights and expertise into new and highly customized solution offerings that they can sell for new revenues, often with high-premiums and/or value-based revenue models that are tied to realized performance improvements in customers' business processes. However, the transition from data-driven services to data-enabled performance outcomes is often difficult and risky; vendors need to be able to guarantee customer outcomes that they might not always fully control, a problem that is compounded by the lack of sufficient data on different customers' processes and assets. Thus, the key barrier that hinders data performatization is usually a lack of the capabilities needed to predict, control, and manage all the key variables (and risks) in customer processes that impact performance outcomes. Compared to product development and the technical and consulting capabilities needed in data productization and data servitization, data performatization requires additional capabilities that extend far into the customer's space and allow vendors to (co-)create and manage performance outcomes on behalf of or together with their customers.

Finally, while the continuum in Fig. 3 implies a unidirectional transition from data and data-enhanced products toward more complex and data-driven services and solutions, it is also possible to move back from complex and customized data solutions to more standardized data (enhanced) products (see also Kowalkowski et al., 2015). For example, while the transition from data and data-enhanced products to data-driven services and solutions appears to be the route companies usually take, we also observed that some companies deliberately took a step back and productized their previously customized services into

more scalable offerings. For example, as the Telia representative explained, “earlier, we did more customized one-off cases for different customers, but our approach nowadays is that we aim for scalability by selling repeatable services to the customers.” Similarly, Kemira has productized its learnings from customer-specific and data-driven consulting services into data products that can be standardized and sold to a larger group of customers. Therefore, depending on their strategic goals and organizational capabilities and as demonstrated across many of our empirical cases, vendors can combine several stages in the data-driven value proposition continuum and make strategic decisions toward the direction in which they want to develop their value propositions in the future.

5. Discussion and implications

5.1. Theoretical implications

The findings of this study make three key contributions. First, we identify *four different data-driven value propositions* (data as a product, data-enhanced products, data-driven services, and data-enabled performance outcomes) that B2B firms can use to sell and monetize data-driven offerings. These findings integrate insights from digital servitization and data monetization literature to identify the key differences of data-driven value propositions that are built on either “pure data” or underlying product or service offerings.

For example, digital servitization research suggests that vendors can build value propositions around core products, product (or process) related services, and performance outcomes and boost these with digital technologies (Coreynen et al. 2017; Kohtamäki et al., 2019; Paiola and Gebauer 2020). However, this view is built on enhancing underlying product offerings with (digital) services and does not unpack the role of data in different value propositions or consider data as a product type of value propositions that are separated from core products. At the same time, data monetization literature highlights value propositions that are built around raw data, data-based insights, or data-driven services (Buff et al. 2015; Gandhi et al., 2018; Parvinen et al., 2020), but it is focused on data-only or data-driven services types of value propositions and does not consider data-enhanced products or data-enabled performance outcomes.

Against this background, we develop an extended categorization of data-driven value propositions that integrates these two perspectives and explains how B2B firms can use data to complement their existing product, service, and outcome offerings or develop completely new data-only type of offerings. This offers more holistic and comparable insights into different types of data-driven value propositions and their unique differences, including the value that they deliver to customers, and the revenue models that vendors can use to capture value for themselves.

Second, we highlight the *key data-related characteristics, capabilities, and challenges* related to each type of value proposition. While previous studies have considered the capabilities and challenges related to data monetization, they consider these at a general level, highlighting, for example, people, platform, and perception-related capabilities (Buff et al. 2015) data, analytical, and IT capabilities (Parvinen et al., 2020), or technical and legal challenges (Mirbagherimarvili et al. 2022). While insightful, these studies do not explain why and how specific data-related capabilities and challenges are more important for different data-driven value propositions than others.

In contrast, our findings highlight the unique and distinctive data-related characteristics, capabilities, and challenges related to specific data-driven value propositions. This shows that there is no “one-size-fits-all” approach when it comes to harnessing and monetizing data, and may help to explain why so many firms still struggle to translate data into profitable value propositions despite increasing investments into data-related capabilities and technologies (Bean and Davenport 2019; Liozu and Ulaga, 2018). A more granular understanding of the specific data-related characteristics, capabilities, and challenges helps firms to

make more informed and strategic decisions when they transition towards specific types of data-driven value propositions.

To facilitate this transition, we develop a *continuum that illuminates how B2B firms can productize, servitize, and performatize* their data resources into value propositions (see Fig. 3). This continuum explains how data-driven value propositions change and evolve during the digital servitization process (Chen et al., 2021) and what are the critical capability bottlenecks and challenges when moving toward more advanced data-driven value propositions (Hasselblatt et al., 2018; Huikkola et al. 2022; Mirbagherimarvili et al. 2022). In particular, it demonstrates how firms can leverage accumulated learnings from data to develop new and enhanced product, service, or outcome offerings. For example, some firms might want to use their accumulated insights from delivering service offerings to expand into more scalable data-only products. Other firms might want to move from data-enhanced products to data-driven service or outcome providers. Overall, by unpacking and distinguishing the productization, servitization, and performatization of data, we shed light on the key decisions that firms must make when they want to monetize their data resources.

Third, and more broadly, our findings highlight the *role of physical and digital assets* in developing data-driven value propositions. Traditionally, the digital servitization literature has focused on equipment manufacturers’ efforts to embed digital features and service elements in their physical product offerings (Kohtamäki et al., 2022). This was also visible in many of our case firms. However, industrial firms can also decouple from their physical assets and engage with “pure data” offerings. For example, Kyndryl has spun off from IBM to become an independent IT infrastructure service provider. In addition to Kyndryl, we have several other distinctively “digital-only” firms in our sample, such as EagleAlpha and Arvova, that sold only value propositions based on pure data (i.e., data as a product). These types of vendors have both potential advantages and some key limitations compared to traditional equipment manufacturers with physical assets. For example, digital-only firms can collect and utilize data from their customers or public sources and act as data curators and brokers. Thus, their value propositions are usually more scalable and involve less friction in onboarding new customers, given that data is easily transferable and replicable (c.f. Jones and Tonetti, 2020). In contrast, equipment manufacturers who embed data features into their physical products, such as mining or forestry equipment, have more limited scalability for data-driven value propositions, as they are often limited to the number of customers using their physical products. However, having access to physical assets that customers are using is also an advantage, as it helps vendors collect and analyze data on how customers are using their products, which is often needed to move towards advanced value propositions that deliver process improvements and performance outcomes in the customers’ own processes.

5.2. Managerial implications

For managers, this study offers several important insights. First, we highlight four different data-driven value propositions and the key data-related capabilities and challenges that vendors need to master to sell and monetize data successfully. Managers should carefully consider how these four types of data-driven value propositions could fit with their own companies’ current or potential offerings and to what extent introducing data-driven elements would enrich or transform their current offerings and business models.

Second, our findings (see Fig. 3 and section 4.5) describe how specific organizational requirements and challenges evolve as firms transition toward more data-driven value propositions. This can help firms to better understand the key opportunities and typical roadblocks that are associated with different data-driven value propositions and the key capabilities they need to acquire and master to excel in each category. For example, while data-driven services and performance outcomes offer more potential for higher revenues and value-based pricing, they

require additional capabilities and more customization and are usually both more expensive and riskier to deploy. In contrast, data products are more standardized and require fewer capabilities, making them potentially attractive options for vendors who want to focus on productizing data and optimizing product sales with fewer investments in the new capabilities needed to deliver complex and highly customized data-driven solutions.

In reality, many firms experiment with multiple data-driven value propositions concurrently, and sell combinations of data products, data-driven services, and data-enabled performance at the same time. Thus, their positions and the corresponding requirements and challenges along the continuum are not clear-cut but tend to overlap in many categories. In these cases, vendors must carefully balance their activities between expanding into new categories and standardizing existing offerings. It is usually advisable to focus on one category in which the vendor has the best relative strengths and capabilities vis-à-vis competitors and then, by using accumulated skills and knowledge, transition slowly to adjacent categories instead of trying to master all the categories simultaneously.

Finally, while selling and monetizing data may sound very attractive, the decision to venture toward data-driven value propositions is not something that vendors can (or should) make overnight in the C-suite. Instead, most firms need a lot of time to carefully develop and pilot new data-driven value propositions with their customers and, during this process, engage in organizational up-skilling, especially in terms of acquiring and developing new capabilities that are related to data collection and analysis, tech architecture, commercialization, sales, and marketing, and ultimately turning data into viable business benefits. While the softer sales and marketing capabilities needed to understand and communicate the value of data-driven value propositions are often possible to learn and (re)train in-house, the more complex technical capabilities related to data collection, analysis, and interpretation usually need to be acquired externally through hiring or partnering with other firms.

5.3. Limitations and future research

While this study offers novel and important insights into selling and monetizing data in B2B markets, it has some natural limitations that highlight opportunities for future research. First, while this study identifies four data-driven value propositions for selling and monetizing data in B2B markets, it is based on qualitative data. Thus, a natural avenue for future research would be to apply quantitative and theory-testing research designs to examine potential performance outcomes, as well as antecedents and moderators of each value proposition. Alternatively, methods like fsQCA could be used to identify the key conditions critical for selling and monetizing data, or experiments could be used to test the effectiveness of data-driven value propositions with different customer segments or decision-makers (Salonen et al. 2021).

Second, while we identified four archetypical data-driven value propositions and their key differences, future studies could delve deeper into each category and examine why and how firms adopt specific types of data-driven value propositions and what individual, organizational, and technological factors and industry characteristics can drive or hinder the adoption of different value propositions (cf. Micallef et al. 2023; Piepponen et al., 2022). Future studies could also examine how firms move between different data-driven value propositions, and how data productization, servitization, and performatization influence and shape this process.

Third, while we draw insights from a diverse set of B2B firms from different industries, they have provided relatively static insights into how firms sell and monetize data. Thus, an interesting avenue for future

research would be to employ more longitudinal research designs and examine how firms initially build or transition toward data-driven value propositions and what kind of organizational and relational dynamics and barriers that might entail. Furthermore, ethnographic research designs (Keränen and Prior 2020) could be used to examine how data shapes frontline employees' or customers' behaviors over time and what kind of social, cultural, and psychological factors drive or hinder the individual and organizational transition toward adopting and delivering data-driven value propositions. Alternatively, future research could also explore and test how different theories can explain how, why, and when specific data-driven value propositions are more (or less) successful (Keränen et al., 2023).

Fourth, while our study covered many different industries and contexts, the landscape of data monetization is evolving rapidly. New types of value propositions and business models are being developed that might fall outside the ones that are highlighted in this study. For example, recent developments on B2B platforms have shown that data is a focal resource that affects how industrial firms' platform business models are governed and how platform owners create and capture value (Jovanovic et al. 2022; Ritala and Jovanovic, 2024). In addition, scholars have identified new types of platform-based business models that utilize different types of governance structures and a variety of ways to monetize open and private data (Kazantsev et al., 2023; Thomas et al., 2023). Furthermore, the rapidly increasing computing power of AI technologies means that B2B firms will have novel opportunities to monetize their internal and external data (Firouzi et al., 2022). Overall, developments in a variety of sectors, combined with advances in digital technologies such as platforms and AI, call for further research on (B2B) data monetization and value propositions.

Finally, future research could focus more explicitly on the role of data in the digital servitization journeys of B2B firms. While creating the infrastructure around collecting and analyzing data via IoT devices, sensors, and platforms is important (Firouzi et al., 2022; Subramaniam et al., 2022), we believe that a focus on *data servitization* (instead of broader "digital servitization") is an interesting and important direction for further inquiry. Such more explicit focus on data could help to recognize how exactly data resources allow firms to capture value by finding data complementarities across data sources and data sets (Ritala and Karhu 2023), and by creating effective market structures and marketplaces for data monetization (Koutroumpis et al. 2020; Thomas et al. 2023). Further research should also examine the more nuanced economic, technical, and legal challenges related to data utilization and data sharing (Mirbagherimarvili et al. 2022; Quach et al., 2022), as these aspects can be very consequential for firms' ability to create and capture value from data (Jones and Tonetti 2020).

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Acknowledgements

Jessica Fishburn has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks (ITN) scheme grant agreement No 956745, EINST4INE: The European Training Network for Industry Digital Transformation across Innovation Ecosystems. The content of this publication does not reflect the official opinion of the EU. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the publication lies entirely with the authors.

Appendix

Interview Guide

- 1) Could you describe your role at your company?
- 2) Can you briefly describe your company's core business?
- 3) What is the role of data in your business and your industry?
- 4) How does your company use or leverage data to create more value for customers?
- 5) Where do you get the data that you sell or use to enhance your offerings?
- 6) What kinds of customer problems does data help you solve?
- 7) What is the added value that customers get from data or data-enhanced offerings?
- 8) What kind of customers usually buy data or data-enhanced offerings?
- 9) What is the role of partners in selling data-enhanced offerings?
- 10) What is the biggest challenge that prevents you from creating value from data for your customers?

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